

Questionnaire results

	How helpful do you think the following activities are for onboarding?						
	Not helpful at all						Very helpful
Mentoring	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Classroom training	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Provide onboarding guideline	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Read technical documentation	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
E-learning	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Orientation session	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Manager Support	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Code review	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Use online portal	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Use online forums	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Start with simple tasks	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Pair programming	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

